

Penugonda: Splendor and Legacy of the Second Capital of Vijayanagara Empire

E N Mounika Sai^{a*}, P.C Venkatasubbaiah^{b*}

^aDepartment of History, SVGM Government Degree College, Kalyandurg, Anantapur District, Andhra Pradesh, India

^bDepartment of History, Archaeology and Culture; Dravidian University, Kuppam, Andhrapradesh, India

Abstract

The article delves into the rich tapestry of the second capital of the Vijayanagara Empire i.e. Penugonda, a focal point of the region named after it as, 'Penugonda Rajya', during Vijayanagara regime was known for its cultural dynamism and architectural brilliance, it flourished as a hub of creativity and innovation during the period under study and it explores the intricate carvings, majestic temples, and grand monuments that characterize the region's built heritage. Drawing on historical accounts and archaeological findings, it illuminates how artistic traditions thrived under Vijayanagara patronage, leaving a lasting legacy that arouses awe and admiration today. Through a detailed examination of its architectural marvels and artistic splendor, this article seeks to uncover the enduring cultural significance of Penugonda within the larger canvas of Vijayanagara art and architecture.

Keywords: Penugonda Rajya, Penugonda, Vijayanagara art and architecture, Cultural heritage, Architectural splendor

The Vijayanagara Empire occupies a prominent place in the study of medieval Indian history. It was founded in AD 1336 by Harihara and Bukka of the Sangama dynasty. They were originally served under the Kakatiya rulers of Warangal. Then they went to Kampili where both were imprisoned and converted to Islam. Later on, they returned to Hindu fold at the initiative of saint Vidyaranya. They also proclaimed their independence and founded a new city on the south bank of Tungabhadra River. It was called 'Vijayanagar' meaning the city of victory. The four dynasties i.e. Sangama, Saluva, Tuluva, and Aravidu, ruled over Vijayanagara with Hampi as their first capital and Penugonda, the second. Sri Krishnadevaraya's reign had been considered one of the most important and glorious periods of Vijayanagara Empire.

Vijayanagara Empire comprised almost the whole of south India to the south of river Krishna. About the boundaries of the empire under Deva Raya II, we have evidence from the Persian ambassador, Abdul Razzak, that the kingdom "extended from Saradip (Ceylon) to those of Kulbarga (Gulbarga), and from Bengal to Malibar. Krishnadevaraya's campaign brought all of southern India under the sway of Vijayanagara. The kingdom marches with all the territory of Bengal, and on the other side with the kingdom of Orya, which is to the east, and to the north with the kingdom of Dakhan, the lands of Ydallco (the Adil Khan, Sultan of Bijapur) and

Ozemelleuco (The Nizam shah, the sultan of Ahmadnagar).¹ The empire had its final fling with destiny during the time of Achyuta Raya in AD 1565 as it suffered a setback after the fateful defeat in the battle of Rakkasa-Tangadi.

The founders Harihara-I and Bukka-I and their immediate successors consolidated their territorial acquisitions who tried to organize the territory by creating new higher-level administrative divisions called rajyas or provinces. 1) There were two rajyas in Tuluva country, Barakur was the capital of the Tulu country, and Mangaluru (Mangalore) was the capital of the southern Tulu country. Other provinces were 2) Araga, Araga-Gutti, or Malerajya (Shimoga district) 3) the Udayagiri rajya 4) the Penugonda rajya 5) the Muluvayi -rajya and 6) the Rajagambhirarajya. Their number varied from time to time. New ones were created depending on the difficulties of administration. Some were reduced in importance, for example, Gutti, a rajya up to the early years of Krishnadevaraya's reign, became a sub-division of Penugonda rajya towards the close of his reign.² The boundaries of provinces or rajyas were changed from time to time to suit immediate administrative needs; and some territories especially, in the northern section of the empire constantly passed to and fro between Vijayanagar and its Muslim enemies, the latter must have experienced many changes in their rule.

Penugonda (14°05'N; 77°36'E) mean a big hill, the town located 70 km away from the Anantapur district headquarters in Andhra Pradesh and forms the taluk headquarters, a major division, and of a block, all bearing the same name. Penugonda is doubtfully identified with Ptolemy's 'pikendaka' as one of the inland cities of Arvarnoi. Tradition claims that it was founded by Kriya Shakti Udaiyar. Earlier this region was controlled by Hoyasala generals governed during the time of Bir Ballala-III, later this region came under the Vijayanagara rulers.³ The area is most picturesquely situated at the foot of a fortified hill over three thousand feet tall. Numerous ruins and fragments of carved stones lie scattered both on the hill and the plains recall the past glory of the place. Archaeological evidence reveal that during the reign of Bukka-I, Penugonda was constructed for his son Virupanna under the guidance of his able minister Anantarasa Chikkavodayar. Virupanna held the governorship of Penugonda for a long time. Some inscriptions reveal that Bukkaraya had a channel dug to bring water from the river pennar to this town, which would appear to be originally the summer resort of Vijayanagara kings of the second dynasty and also gives information about Harihara-II and Devaraya-II, who governed from this headquarters. During the reign of Devaraya-II, his younger brother Pratapadevaraya was mentioned as having a high office and acquired the rule of Ghanadri from his elder brother in AD 1424. In the Saluva period also the Penugonda region attained a center of provincial importance and continued.

During the rule of Sri Krishnadevaraya, he appointed strong Dandanayakas as the governor such as Rayasam Kondamarasa, who held this high position in Udayagiri rajya also. It is interesting to note that, Rayasam Kondamarasa, the Rayas subordinate performed the Lakshahoma ceremony, at Penugonda for the success of the king's army. Penugonda regained its glory after the battle of Rakshasa Tangadi in AD 1565. This battle is generally considered to mark the end of the greatness of Vijayanagara, although the Kingdom lingered on for almost a hundred years under the Aravidu Dynasty. Penugonda continued to flourish as the capital of Aravidu dynasty rulers of Vijayanagara starting with Tirumalaraya until as they changed their

capital to Chandragiri. Later Tirumala divided the empire into three provinces and placed his three sons in charge for each one of them. One of his sons Sriranga became the ruler of Telugu areas as his province headquarters. At this time Penugonda became the target for Muslim attacks frequently. In AD 1576, Bijapur sultan Ali Adilshah I, led an army against Sriranga to seize Penugonda. In this battle, Sriranga was defeated by the sultan and left for Chandragiri.

Penugoda rajya extended over the northern part of Gutti rajya, the southern part of Chandragiri rajya, north-western part of Udayagiri rajya. It comprised the places of Sira and Pavagada Taluks of Bellary, Tumkur district, Bagepalli Taluk of Kolar district, parts of Anantapur district (including Penugonda Taluk), and parts of Northern Mysore region in Karnataka.⁴The practice of appointing members of the royal family as Governors or Mahamandalesvaras of provinces, followed by the Pallavas, the Cholas, and the Hoyasalas has been adopted by the Vijayanagara rulers. When Harihara-I was the king, Marapa was the ruler of the province of Araga with its capital at Chandragutti.⁵ Sri Ranga-II, son of Tirumala appointed as the viceroy of the home province, Penugonda. The most important duty of the provincial governor was to protect his province from the attacks of the enemy. He was also the revenue officer of the province and probably acted as its chief magistrate. He was responsible for preserving law and order in the province. He enjoyed the right to impose new taxes or remit old ones.⁶ Nuniz mentions some of the governors of the kingdom, the revenue they held, the name of their provinces, and their military and financial obligations to the imperial government. Ajaparcetimapa, who was a governor of Hudogary (Udayagiri), Condovin (Kondavid), Penagundim (Pennukonda), Codegaral (Kanigiri, Nellore district), Cidaota (Siddhout or Siddharattam, Cuddapah district) - income was 8,00,000 pardaos of Gold and his military contribution was 25,000 foot, 1,500 horses, 40 elephants, and his Annual financial contribution to the King was 3,00,000 Pardaos.⁷

Penugonda was chosen as the second capital of the Vijayanagara Empire due to its strategic location along trade routes, strong defensive position, administrative efficiency, cultural significance, and the need to decentralize power for better governance. A major defensive system of Vijayanagara was Penugonda Fort, which is located in the region and has a rich history dating back to the Vijayanagara Empire, known for its impressive art and architecture. The art and architecture of Penugonda Fort were influenced by various regional styles and artistic traditions prevalent during the Vijayanagara period.⁸This included influences from the Chalukyan, Hoysala, and Chola architectural styles, blending them into a unique Vijayanagara aesthetic.⁹ Penugonda Fort was strategically built on a hill, providing natural defenses, and was further fortified with strong walls and bastions. The layout included various sections for residential, administrative, and military purposes. The entrance gateways (gopurams) of Penugonda Fort exhibited typical Vijayanagara architectural features such as towering structures adorned with intricate carvings of gods, goddesses, mythical creatures, and floral motifs.¹⁰ These were often made of stone and elaborately decorated. Within the fort complex, several temples and religious structures were constructed. These temples followed the traditional Dravidian style of architecture, characterized by pyramid-shaped towers (vimanas) and pillared halls (mandapas).¹¹ The sculptures and carvings on these temples showcased scenes from Hindu mythology, reflecting the cultural and religious ethos of the Vijayanagara period. Penugonda Fort was also home to palaces and residences of the Vijayanagara kings and

nobles. These structures featured ornate carvings, frescoes, and elaborate courtyards, indicating the wealth and artistic patronage of the rulers. Like other Vijayanagara sites, Penugonda Fort had advanced water management systems such as tanks, reservoirs, and wells.¹² These ensured a sustainable water supply for the fort's inhabitants and were often integrated into the overall architectural plan. As a fort, Penugonda also featured military architecture such as bastions, ramparts, and defensive structures. These elements were designed to withstand sieges and attacks, showcasing the engineering prowess of the period. Overall, Penugonda Fort stands as a testament to the grandeur and architectural splendor of the Vijayanagara Empire, combining artistic finesse with strategic design to create a significant historical and cultural landmark. This fort was one of the best defenses of the Vijayanagara kingdom.¹³ With the decline of the Vijayanagara kingdom, the Sultan of Golconda captured this fort. Later Mysore Kingdom captured this fort briefly until the British overtook it after the fall of Tipu Sultan.

Gagan Mahal, located within Penugonda Fort in Andhra Pradesh, India, is a notable structure from the Vijayanagara period known for its distinct art and architecture. Gagan Mahal exemplifies the Indo-Islamic architectural style prevalent during the Vijayanagara period, showcasing a blend of Hindu and Islamic influences. This fusion is typical of the cultural syncretism that characterized Vijayanagara architecture.¹⁴ Gagan Mahal is a large and imposing palace structure built with a central hall flanked by two wings. The central hall is particularly noteworthy for its size and the intricacy of its design. It was likely used for royal audiences, courtly ceremonies, and other important functions. The palace features intricate carvings and decorative motifs on its walls, arches, and pillars. These carvings often depict floral patterns, geometric designs, and occasionally, figurative sculptures. These elements highlight the artistic skills and craftsmanship of the artisans during the Vijayanagara period. The archways and facades of Gagan Mahal are adorned with elaborate stucco work and plaster decorations. These decorations include intricate patterns and motifs that enhance the visual appeal of the palace. The construction materials used in Gagan Mahal include locally sourced stone and lime mortar, which were typical for Vijayanagara architecture. These materials were not only durable but also allowed for the intricate detailing seen in the palace's design. Beyond its aesthetic value, the Gagan Mahal was designed to serve practical purposes, providing comfortable living quarters for the royal family and serving as a venue for administrative and ceremonial activities. Gagan Mahal's architecture reflects the cosmopolitan nature of the Vijayanagara Empire, which embraced diverse cultural influences while maintaining its distinctive identity. This blend of styles and influences contributed to the empire's rich cultural heritage. Its grandeur and artistic sophistication make it a notable historical and cultural landmark from the Vijayanagara period in southern India.¹⁵

Timmarasu Jail in Penugonda, during the Vijayanagara period, holds historical significance primarily due to its association with Timmarasu, the chief minister and trusted advisor of Emperor Krishnadevaraya. While specific details about Timmarasu Jail's architecture are scarce, understanding its historical context and its role during that period provides insight into its importance.¹⁶ Timmarasu, also known as Tenali Ramakrishna, was a legendary figure in the court of Emperor Krishnadevaraya of the Vijayanagara Empire. He was known for his wisdom, wit, and loyalty to the emperor. Timmarasu's presence in Penugonda and the establishment of

a jail associated with him suggest the administrative and strategic importance of the region during that era. Timmarasu Jail likely served as a detention or administrative center within Penugonda, where prisoners or individuals deemed threats to the empire could be housed. During the Vijayanagara period, such facilities were crucial for maintaining law and order and for consolidating imperial control over distant territories like Penugonda. While specific architectural details of Timmarasu Jail are not extensively documented, it would have likely followed the architectural conventions of Vijayanagara structures.¹⁷ Penugonda, where Timmarasu Jail was located, held strategic importance as a fortified stronghold and administrative center during the Vijayanagara period. It served as a military base and a key location for overseeing the eastern territories of the empire. Timmarasu's legacy extends beyond the jail named after him. He is celebrated in folklore and literature for his wit and wisdom, and his association with Emperor Krishnadevaraya highlights the cultural vibrancy and intellectual milieu of the Vijayanagara court.

Basava Well, also known as Basava Bavi, is a significant historical structure from the Vijayanagara period, located in Penugonda. Basava Well was primarily constructed to provide a reliable and sustainable source of water for the inhabitants in the region, of the Vijayanagara Empire. It served as a vital water source for both daily use and during times of siege or conflict.¹⁸ It reflects the empire's emphasis on urban planning and infrastructure development to support its growing population and administrative needs. Basava Well holds cultural significance in the region. It is named after Basava, the sacred bull (Nandi) of Lord Shiva, which underscores its religious importance in the Hindu context. The well is typically constructed in a stepped pyramidal form, descending several meters into the ground. This design not only facilitates access to water but also ensures structural stability. The construction materials used include locally available stone and lime mortar, typical of Vijayanagara architecture. The stones were meticulously laid to create a sturdy structure capable of enduring centuries. Basava Well also features ornate carvings and sculptures around its opening and along the steps. These carvings depict motifs of gods, goddesses, mythical creatures, and floral patterns, showcasing the empire's artistic sophistication and religious symbolism.¹⁹ The well's design ensured efficient water management and conservation, reflecting the empire's understanding of hydrology and urban planning. The steps leading down into the well were designed for ease of access, allowing people to draw water even during times when the water level was lower. The architecture thus combined functionality with aesthetic and practical considerations and its construction reflects the empire's commitment to urban planning, water management, and cultural symbolism, making it a key landmark in understanding the Vijayanagara period's achievements and legacy.

In conclusion, the article vividly illustrates the enduring legacy of the Vijayanagara Empire, particularly through its influence on Penugonda's history and architecture. The remnants of this illustrious period, such as the Gagan Mahal, Timmarasu Jail, Penugonda Fort, and Basava Well, stand as a testament to the empire's rich cultural and architectural heritage. These structures not only showcase the artistic prowess of the Vijayanagara artisans but also serve as poignant reminders of the empire's political and administrative significance in South India. By delving into Penugonda's history and highlighting its architectural marvels, the article

underscores the lasting impact of the Vijayanagara Empire, echoing through time and enriching our understanding of India's vibrant past.

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